

WGISS - Working Group for Information Systems and Services

CEOS is GEO's "space arm" coordinating the provision of space data to the Global Earth Observation System of Systems

WGISS (The Working Group on Information Systems and Services) is a subsidiary body supporting CEOS.

How should the UK Earth Observation AI and Machine Learning Community engage ?

- UK network /mailing list for UK AI and Machine Learning
- Participation in the Technology Exploration Interest Group
- Project Presentations at CEOS WGISS meetings
- Contribution to CEOS projects
- Local discussion of infrastructure or Data needs

For further Information please contact:
 Esther Conway
 Senior Earth Observation Data Scientist
 Centre for Environmental Data Archival
 Email : esther.conway@stfc.ac.uk
 CEOS website: <http://ceos.org/>
 UK GEO/CEOS office: <https://www.nceo.ac.uk/innovation/nceo-geo/>